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Synthesis of Some New Heteropoly Salts

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IN this communication three distinctly new heteropoly salts of molybdenum, vanadium and tungsten with 1:6, central:condensing atom ratio are reported.

The conditions of formations are the same as has been discussed in the previous communications^{1,2}. The pH were maintained rigorously throughout the experiment.

6-Sodium tungstomanganate :

50 ml of .2M sodium tungstate, 45 ml of 0.05M manganese sulphate and 14 ml of glacial acetic acid were mixed together (pH 3.64), stirred vigorously for one hour, kept in a steam bath for three hours and left for crystallisation. Greyish white powdery compound was collected after an interval of seven days. The compound was analysed chemically and colorimetrically : (Found : Mn, 2.21 ; W, 48.23 ; Na, 1.00 ; H 2.25 ; calcd. for Na₁₀[MnW₆O₂₄]28H₂O : Mn, 2.41 ; W, 48.48 ; Na, 1.10 ; H, 2.45 per cent).

6-Ammonium molybdochromate :

Solutions of 50 ml of 0.05M ammonium molybdate, 40 ml of .05M potassium dichromate and 20 ml of glacial acetic acid were mixed together rapidly at pH 2.8, digested for three hours, evaporated to crystallisation on a water bath and left overnight ; orange coloured flaky powdery compound was separated after an interval of five days. From analysis : (Found : Cr, 4.02 ; Mo, 46.72 ; N, 6.62 ; H, 3.32 ; calcd. for : (NH₄)₆ [CrMo₆O₂₄] 10H₂O : Cr, 4.22 ; Mo, 46.90 ; N, 6.68 ; H, 3.58 ; per cent).

6-Potassium vanadochromate :

Solutions of 50 ml of .013M ammonium metavanadate, 43 ml of .05M potassium dichromate and 14 ml of glacial acetic acid were mixed by constant stirring (pH 2.4) for half an hour, digested for two hours and crystallised on a steam bath. After an interval of ten days brick-red shining crystals were collected from analysis : (Found : Cr, 5.22 ; V, 31.83 ; K, 8.03 ; H, 2.31 ; calcd. for K₃[CrV₆O₁₉]12H₂O : Cr, 5.43 ; V, 32.00 ; K, 8.15 ; H, 2.51 per cent).

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Some Bipositive Cations with 6-Mercaptopurine and Thioguanine in Solution

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6-MERCAPTOPURINE (MCP) and 2-amino-6-mercaptopurine (thioguanine, TGN) have been introduced in human cancer therapy, and has proved effective as anticancer agent in comparison to other purine derivatives like adenine and TGN. MCP and TGN having similar structures, form chelates with metal ions, which probably determine their activities.

The present communication deals with attempts to study mixed complexes of MCP and TGN with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II), using 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) or 2,2'-bipyridine (bipy) as primary ligands. Studies with Cu(II) and Zn(II) were not possible.

Chelating reactions between the above metal ions and MCP have been described by Freiser *et al*¹, while TGN complexes with Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Pb(II), UO₂(VI), Ca(II) and Mg(II) have been reported earlier². Formation constants of the mixed complexes have been determined using a modified form of Irving-Rossotti titration technique^{3,4}.

Experimental

All materials used were of reagent grade. Stock solutions (0.01M) of phen and bipy were prepared in water. 0.01M solutions of MCP and TGN were freshly prepared by dissolving in 0.02M alkali. Solutions of metal nitrates were prepared and standardized against EDTA⁵.

pH measurements were done using an Elico pH meter (model LI-10) with glass (EK-62A) and calomel electrodes. The pH meter was calibrated with 0.05M potassium hydrogen phthalate solution.

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The pH meter reading was converted into hydrogen ion concentration using the method of Van Uitert and Haas⁹.

Procedure: Mixtures for titrations were prepared as described earlier¹⁰, using HNO₃, KNO₃, primary ligand and secondary ligand. The ionic strengths were 0.1M (KNO₃) and measurements were made at 25°, the media being 50% (v/v) ethanol. The alkali present in secondary ligand solution was preneutralized by equivalent amount of acid.

In the discussion the curves A to E represent those corresponding to the titrations of the various mixtures¹⁰ (Figs. being omitted).

Results and Discussion

On being titrated phen, gives a sharp inflexion at $a=2$ (a =moles of KOH per mole of ligand) at lower pH. At higher pH, the secondary ligand curve(D) departs from the acid curve(A). When 1:1 metal+primary ligand solution was titrated, one inflexion at $a=2$ was observed which indicates the formation of a 1:1 complex in the lower pH region. In this system precipitation starts after $a=2$.

1:1:1::M:A:L solution on being titrated diverges from 1:1 MA curve(C) after pH 4, and precipitation starts after $a=3$. Curves E and C follow the same path upto pH~4, and then E diverges from C. When the formation of 1:1 MA is complete, the combination of L to MA takes place and additional alkali is required to neutralize the liberated protons due to the formation of mixed complex MAL.

The formation of the mixed complex is confirmed from a comparison of the theoretical composite curve and experimental curve, as well as from the observation that in the mixed ligand chelate titration curve E, no precipitation is observed upto $a=3$, while in the binary chelate, ML⁺ precipitates in the very beginning.

The formation constant⁷ was calculated from the following equation

$$K_{MAL} = \frac{\bar{n}_{MAL}}{(n - \bar{n}_{MAL})[L]_{MAL}^n} \quad (1)$$

the various quantities being obtained using method of Goldberg⁸, the symbols having the usual meaning.

Only one protonation (pK=7.85) constant has been evaluated in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium

under the experimental conditions. The ionization of proton from neutral MCP occurs from the mercapto-group⁹, while the second ionization from the imino group has not been observed, which appears to take place at a very high pH. Similarly, the ionization from TGN (pK=8.63) is for the thio group.

Binary Cu(II) and Zn(II) complexes precipitate, and with MCP Cu(II) gets reduced to Cu(I)¹¹. The binary chelates of all metal ions viz. Co(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) with MCP or TGN are insoluble in 50% aqueous ethanol and could not be studied. The mixed ligand chelates with Co(II) and Ni(II) are soluble and their stability constants are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND CHELATES IN 50% (v/v) ETHANOL, (25°, $\mu=0.1M$)

System	log K_{MAL}
Ni(II)-phen-MCP	5.21 ± 0.01
Co(II)-phen-MCP	4.58 ± 0.01
Ni(II)-phen-TGN	5.65 ± 0.02
Co(II)-phen-TGN	5.18 ± 0.01
Ni(II)-bipy-MCP	5.19 ± 0.02
Co(II)-bipy-MCP	4.75 ± 0.01
Ni(II)-bipy-TGN	5.61 ± 0.01
Co(II)-bipy-TGN	5.17 ± 0.01

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